

Sample Case Study Prompt and Student Instructions Handout_2

CASE. CD40 Ligand Deficiency (Hyper IgM Syndrome)

Case Studies in Immunology. A Clinical Companion. 7e Garland Science

SUMMARY

B cells require co-stimulatory help from CD4⁺ T cells to become fully activated. Signal 1 is the recognition and binding of the specific antigen by the B cell receptor (BCR), which is taken into the cell via receptor-mediated endocytosis. The presentation of peptide antigens in the context of MHC Class II to T cells in the peripheral lymphoid organs allows for T cells to recognize and bind, if TCR specificity is a match. TCR recognition of peptide antigens presented by a B cell results in upregulation of CD40L (CD40 ligand/CD154) on the T cell. CD40L on the T cell interacts with CD40 on the B cell (signal 2). Alongside T cell secreted cytokines (signal 3), the CD40-CD40L co-stimulatory interaction helps B cells become activated, differentiate, and if ‘instructed’ to do so by the cytokines released, isotype switch. Isotype switching is the process whereby B cells recombine their previously rearranged variable region (that confers antigen binding specificity) with a new constant region gene downstream of μ and d , resulting in a different isotype (that confers effector function). The result is that a B cell switches from the production of IgM antibodies to IgG, IgA, or IgE antibody isotypes, while keeping the same variable (or antigen-binding) region. Without the CD40-CD40L interaction, B cell differentiation to memory cells and class switching does not occur, resulting in B cells that are confined to producing IgM. As this case report explores, individuals with CD40L deficiency accumulate IgM and are susceptible to a wide range of infections due to impaired B cell and T cell interaction and the absence of the production of IgG, IgA and IgE isotypes.

CASE STUDY PREPARATION INSTRUCTIONS (TO DO BEFORE CLASS)

Please complete the following sections of the module before our class meeting.

1. Read “Case. CD40 Ligand Deficiency (aka Hyper IgM Syndrome) Week 3.pdf”.
2. Review and be prepared to discuss the “Discussion Questions” listed below. NOTE: the questions below differ from those in the pdf.

3. Bring your own questions to class to be thoroughly prepared to contribute to the interactive discussion session. We will discuss the questions listed below in class and/or any student-driven questions that arise throughout the discussion session. If time allows, we may choose to discuss the questions found at the end of the case.

Remember, you will receive points for your appropriate participation during case study discussions. Participation includes providing answers to discussion questions and/or asking questions of your own!

DISCUSSION QUESTIONS

1. Can you hypothesize which immunoglobulin isotypes (and associated immune mechanisms) might be particularly suited to respond to a respiratory virus infection? An opportunistic bacterial infection of skin? A tumor cell? Fig. 2.1 in the case report will be helpful!
2. If a B cell has isotype switched to express IgE, which isotypes could it hypothetically express in the future? Why?
3. What is the rationale for the experiment in Fig. 2.5? What does the binding of cells to either soluble CD40 or anti-CD25 (alpha chain of the IL-2R) tell us?
4. Why might Dennis have been able to make antibodies against blood group A and B antigens, but not tetanus toxoid, typhoid O and H, or streptolysin antigens?
5. How might Dennis respond to mRNA vaccination? Would you expect these to be efficacious in individuals with Hyper-IgM Syndrome?
6. Why is a lack of germinal centers in Dennis's lymph node biopsies consistent with CD40L deficiency?
7. How does hematopoietic stem cell transplantation cure individuals with Hyper IgM Syndrome? Why do donors need to be "HLA identical"?
8. Why would Hyper IgM Syndrome be more common among males? Why are CD40 deficiencies rarer than CD40L deficiencies?

VIDEOS – OPTIONAL to WATCH BEFORE CLASS for further exploration of the topic

- Robert Wood Johnson Foundation Reimagining Medical Education 'Introduction to the Human Immune System' video (11:12min)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2wrTpWnfy8I&list=PLkdHelTIDZnF45aLNx62FCx7qpkqbeXao&index=7>

- Hyper IgM Syndrome Conference (23:47min)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ccqeKM3FPuU>

The **Instructor Answers to the Discussion Questions** are available upon request. Please contact Aimee Bernard (Aimee.Bernard@cuanschultz.edu).

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